

Issues and Causal Factors in Machine Learning Methods for Predicting Epileptic Seizures Using EEG: Towards Clinically Viable Prediction via Utility–Latency Feasibility Constraints

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Abstract

Approximately one in three people with epilepsy have drug-refractory epilepsy, which means they continue to have seizures despite medication. This neurological disorder, characterized by abnormal electrical activity in the brain, can lead to involuntary movements, loss of consciousness, and even death. In this review, we identify the challenges involved in developing machine learning models for EEG-based seizure prediction, with emphasis on critical stages including dataset design, preprocessing, feature extraction, classification, and post-processing. The main contribution of this work is to propose a classification of these problems based on the development process, distinguishing between pipeline-based and non-pipeline-based problems, with the aim of guiding current research toward real-world implementation. We explore the underlying causes of these problems and highlight proposed solutions from the literature. In conclusion, there is a pressing need to develop algorithms that achieve an optimal balance between efficiency and performance while ensuring interpretability. Additionally, establishing a standardized framework for their comparison is essential.

Keywords: issues, seizure prediction, machine learning, EEG, epilepsy

1. Introduction

Epilepsy is one of the most prevalent neurological disorders, affecting more than 50 million people worldwide [1,2]. Despite major advances in pharmacological treatments, approximately 30% of patients continue to experience uncontrolled seizures, highlighting the urgent need for reliable seizure prediction strategies [1,3]. In this context, machine learning (ML) methods have emerged as promising tools for analyzing electroencephalography (EEG) signals and predicting seizures before onset, with the potential to substantially improve patient safety, autonomy, and quality of life [4-6]. However, despite notable progress, achieving accurate, robust, and clinically deployable seizure prediction remains a major challenge [7].

This difficulty arises largely from the intrinsic complexity of EEG signals and the variability of preictal dynamics. EEG recordings are highly non-stationary, noisy, and patient-specific, while the preictal state itself often exhibits subtle, heterogeneous, and inconsistently expressed patterns across individuals and recording conditions [8,9]. As a result, models that perform well in controlled experimental settings may fail to generalize across patients, datasets, or acquisition environments [10–12]. Data reliability is therefore a central challenge: differences in electrode placement, device quality, acquisition protocols, and environmental noise can significantly affect signal quality and downstream model

performance. These issues become particularly relevant in real-world settings, where seizure prediction systems may need to operate across hospitals, outpatient clinics, and home-based wearable monitoring platforms [10,13,14].

Traditional seizure prediction approaches frequently rely on handcrafted features (e.g., spectral power descriptors or engineered statistical measures), which can be effective in constrained settings but often require substantial domain expertise, extensive preprocessing, and careful tuning [6,15]. Such pipelines may be difficult to reproduce and adapt when signal characteristics or hardware configurations change. More recently, deep learning (DL) models, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), have shown strong potential by learning complex temporal and spatial representations directly from EEG data, reducing dependence on manual feature design [15,16]. Nevertheless, these advances introduce new challenges, including high computational cost, dependence on large training datasets, limited scalability for real-time or resource-constrained deployment, and reduced transparency of decision-making [17–20]. In clinical contexts, this lack of interpretability remains a critical barrier because clinicians require understandable and trustworthy predictions to support decision-making [21,22].

Beyond model architecture, progress in the field is further hindered by the lack of standardized evaluation and reporting practices. Differences in preprocessing pipelines, patient partitioning strategies, validation schemes, prediction horizons, post-processing logic, and performance metrics make fair comparisons across studies difficult and often

misleading. Consequently, the literature contains many methods with encouraging reported performance, yet limited evidence of real-world clinical utility or deployability.

To address this gap, the main contribution of this work is a process-oriented causal classification that distinguishes between pipeline-based and non-pipeline-based problems in EEG-based seizure prediction research. This classification provides a unifying framework for organizing the literature according to where and how limitations emerge—either within the algorithm development pipeline (e.g., preprocessing, feature extraction, modeling, post-processing) or beyond it (e.g., evaluation inconsistency, lack of standardization, interpretability, and comparability).

In addition, and as a central original element of this review, we introduce a clinically grounded viability layer that complements the causal taxonomy by linking algorithmic performance to real-world applicability. Specifically, we frame clinical adoption in terms of a Utility–Latency feasibility region, which captures whether a seizure prediction system is both (i) clinically beneficial (e.g., balancing true warnings against false alarms) and (ii) clinically actionable (e.g., delivering warnings with sufficient lead time). This perspective helps explain why strong classification metrics alone may not translate into clinical usefulness and provides a practical lens for interpreting trade-offs between predictive performance, false alarm burden, and system latency.

Within this integrated framework, we identify recurring limitations such as poor predictive robustness and low computational efficiency (pipeline-based), as well as limited interpretability and difficulties in fair model comparison (non-pipeline-based). Based on the reviewed literature, we also discuss solutions and recommendations aimed at improving

methodological rigor, clinical relevance, and translational potential in future seizure prediction research.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Section 2 deals with ML and DL algorithms used in the field of seizure prediction; Section 3 is devoted to the assessment of pipeline-based problems. In Section 4, non-pipeline based-problems are described.

2. Methodology of Review

This work adopts a narrative review approach with a scoping perspective to identify and critically examine methodological and translational challenges in EEG-based epileptic seizure prediction using machine learning. The literature search focused on original peer-reviewed studies proposing machine learning or deep learning models for seizure prediction and reporting quantitative performance metrics. Searches were conducted across major scientific databases, including Scopus, PubMed, and IEEE Xplore, using combinations of keywords such as “epilepsy,” “seizure prediction,” “machine learning,” and “EEG.” Studies were included if they presented algorithmic models applied to EEG-based seizure

prediction and provided sufficient methodological detail to enable critical assessment. Rather than restricting the analysis to explicitly stated limitations, challenges were identified through critical examination of dataset selection, preprocessing strategies, feature extraction, model design, post-processing, evaluation protocols, and reported outcomes. Based on this analysis, challenges were organized into pipeline-based and non-pipeline-based categories. This approach enables the synthesis of methodological bottlenecks and systemic barriers that hinder clinical translation.

3. Algorithmic epileptic seizure prediction

Creating machine learning models for epileptic seizure prediction depends on a complex pipeline that comprises several phases: data collection, preprocessing, feature extraction, model selection/training, and postprocessing (Fig.1). Each stage is essential to ensure the reliability and robustness of the predictive system in clinical and real-world applications [7,23]. Traditional, conventional machine learning methods for seizure prediction have centered intensely on feature engineering, where domain knowledge is utilized to extract significant metrics from EEG signals [24]. Features such as power spectral density ratios, entropy measures, and wavelet coefficients have been popular [13,25]. A problem behind these popularity is that they frequently require thorough preprocessing phases like artifact removal and signal normalization to make the data less noisy and less variable [9,26]. Also handmade features, which look practical, can lack adaptability, which reduces their effectiveness in the context where EEG patterns differ from training data [27,28]. Now, these features are important because conventional ML models, e.g., support vector machines (SVMs) and decision trees, astounding models in seizure detection and prediction, rely on them, but as a result of overfitting or limited data sources these techniques may have difficulty generalizing across diverse patients [29]. DL has arisen as an encouraging choice for automating feature extraction in many tasks, particularly in predicting seizures. As an example in 2024, [30] displayed a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model to automatically extract features from EEG records, attaining 97% in validation accuracy.

CNNs and RNNs have shown an outstanding quality in pinpointing complex spatiotemporal patterns from raw EEG dataset [31]. In [31], the author merged CNN and LSTM networks which could grasp such patterns to predict seizures obtaining a sensitivity of approximately 97%, and 0.2373/hour as false positive rate. Correspondingly, in 2018, [32] combined CNN and gated recurrent units (GRUs) to detect seizures, getting 30% sensitivity at six false alarms per day. These studies highlight the success of CNNs and RNNs in identifying spatial and temporal patterns, consequently boosting the accuracy and reliability of seizure prediction systems. By encompassing pretrained knowledge and allowing decentralized privacy-preserving model updates, advances in transfer learning and federated learning have improved generalization across patients [33]. Federated learning is a non-centralized system facilitating training throughout multiple institutions,

but preserving private medical information [9]. Despite these remarkable improvements, high computational cost [34], large-scale training datasets requirements [35], and limited or lack of interpretability [36] are significant barriers to widespread implementation of such algorithms. The unification of the strengths of conventional, DL and current methods help researchers aim to handle these barriers, i.e., to optimize ML/DL models for real-world deployment under different environments such as hospitals and domestic care. Now, we shall describe all the pipeline phases in the development of ML and DL models to predict seizures.

Figure 1: Seizure prediction pipeline focused on machine learning and deep learning methods using EEG signals

2.1. Dataset

It is the first pipeline phase and provides the basis for the development of a seizure prediction model [23,37]. It plays a vital role in the accuracy and efficiency results, and also in the feasibility of model comparison [38,39]. [40] shows us that the structure and quality of the main element in this step, which is EEG data, substantially impact the ability of the model to capture patterns, and consequently affect generalization to new data. Correspondingly, by revealing the seizure prediction model to a broad diversity of scenarios, [41] stresses that a well-structured data, with samples of seizures and non seizures, improves the performance of the model. It is seen that poorly structured data make it harder for the model to generalize [41]. [42] and [43] observe and discuss the fact that imbalances in data can contribute to

biases, reducing the effectiveness of the seizure prediction model. Also, the execution of the dataset step may have a direct effect on both efficiency and model comparison. [44] observe that the size, balance and structure of data impact the effectiveness of the

model in processing information when managing large scale EEG recordings. In [45], authors highlight that standardized datasets are crucial for impartial model comparison. Basically, without a uniform data, model performance variance may be caused by data heterogeneity rather than algorithmic dissimilarities.

2.2. Preprocessing

The main goal of preprocessing EEG signals is to improve data quality by removing artifacts and noise [46,47]. This preprocessing is performed using several techniques including filtering, artifact removal, and domain transformations [26,39,46,48]. It has been shown that the design of preprocessing procedures can affect subsequent results of EEG data analysis [26,50,51]. Especially in seizure prediction, because this is the first algorithmic step in a general process to develop a ML technique, it is therefore necessary to remove noise and artifacts optimally by balancing performance and efficiency [39,48]. The latter is relevant to aim for a real application in the future, however it remains a challenge in developing algorithms for EEG signal preprocessing [47,49,50,51].

2.3. Feature extraction

One of the main goals of feature extraction from EEG signals is dimensionality reduction and data compaction [52,53]. The most common features extracted are statistical features in the time domain and spectral moments in the frequency domain [49,54,55]. One of the key aspects of research to detect and predict epileptic seizures using EEG signals is this phase [56]. However, this stage faces the challenge that feature engineering must be performed manually and individually for each patient [52,53,57]. This requires specialized knowledge in the area and, as a consequence, can result in a low level of accuracy when using other datasets due to the lack of generalization in feature extraction [58].

2.4. ML classifier model

The ML classifier model phase involves selecting, designing, and training algorithms to distinguish between seizure and non-seizure events from EEG data [59]. Its success depends on how well the model learns patterns to generalize across patients and conditions. Pivotal challenges in this phase cover avoiding poor testing performance, warranting high efficiency, sustaining interpretability, and lowering the complexity of comparisons, all these arise from the restraints of the classifiers employed [59,60,61,62,63]. While data quality and preprocessing phase plainly exert influence on the ultimate model performance, the classifier's architecture becomes uppermost in determining its terminal efficacy. The structural blueprint of the classifier elaborately rules how it grasps and processes filtered data, and how effectively it apprehends fundamental patterns [42]. A well-designed classifier permits the whole model to balance computational efficiency and predictive accuracy, optimizing performance over sundry datasets [64]. As a consequence,

while data preprocessing diminishes issues such as noise or bias, the classifier’s architecture proceeds as the foremost mechanism for removing relevant insights, ensuring robust model outcomes [42]. For instance, seizure detection and prediction methods that employ classifiers in most cases surpass non-classifier-based approaches [4,59,65]. Classical machine learning methods, such as Random Forest, and SVM, are commonly utilized in this stage. However, these procedures become less efficient when handling high-volume EEG data due to their insufficient ability to process huge and complex data [66,67]. Among deep learning algorithms, LSTM networks have shown to be good performing models in these cases, thanks to their ability to manage time-dependent data [68,69]. The selection of ML and DL algorithms directly influences the performance of epilepsy prediction models [11,39]. While some algorithms are more stable across datasets, others are highly sensitive to specific data characteristics, making it difficult to achieve consistent results [11,70].

2.5. Post Processing

In this stage, the refinement of raw output of the seizure prediction model occurs in order to ensure reliable predictions to be used in the clinical context [71]. There is a reduction of false alarms, addressing factors that impact the accuracy and efficiency of the model [72]. One key challenge in ML/DL development with real-world application is handling the false positive ratio. The seizure prediction model may produce many incorrect outcomes, overwhelming clinicians with unnecessary alerts, if the post processing phase does not include filters for false alarms [6]. Smoothing temporal consistency of predictions results to be crucial in the model applicability since abrupt transitions in prediction can lead to missed seizure warnings or delayed responses [6,73]. Another critical factor is threshold optimization. A poor optimization of it can result in failing to detect seizure or giving too many false positives, both compromising model performance [74,75].

Segment-based models analyze fixed-length EEG segments, while event-based models focus on detecting entire seizure events [11]. These distinctions influence how predictions are processed and validated, ultimately affecting the clinical applicability of the seizure prediction model. Event-based models utilize postprocessing techniques to interpret continuous EEG data and predict the onset of seizures.

3. Issues in machine learning methods

Machine learning methods for epileptic seizure prediction face multiple technical and conceptual barriers that limit their translation from research to clinical practice. Based on a critical synthesis, we propose classifying these challenges into two main groups: pipeline-based and non-pipeline-based problems. The first group comprises issues that originate within the algorithmic development pipeline from data acquisition to decision making. The second group encompasses broader systemic or methodological limitations

that do not originate in the pipeline, including the lack of standardization, interpretability, and transparency across studies.

This dual classification provides a causal framework to understand how problems arise and propagate across the development of EEG-based ML models for seizure prediction, ultimately constraining their reliability, interpretability, and clinical applicability.

3.1. Pipeline-based problems

Pipeline-based problems refer to challenges that arise within specific stages of the machine learning workflow for seizure prediction such as, dataset, preprocessing, feature extraction, classification, and even postprocessing [78,79], see Figure 2.

Each issue is identified according to the phase of the pipeline in which it originates, although their effects often propagate to subsequent stages, amplifying the uncertainty of the prediction and affecting the efficiency, performance, robustness and clinical applicability of the model [76] [77] [80]. The following subsections describe the main factors at the pipeline level, explain their impact, and suggest possible solutions to the problem based on the literature.

Figure 2: Overview of pipeline-based problems in machine learning methods for seizure prediction using EEG signals.

3.1.1. Rarity of Seizures

Epileptic seizure prediction faces significant challenges due to the low incidence of seizure events [81,82]. This phenomenon manifests as data scarcity, since the limited frequency of seizures available for training hinders the development of robust and generalizable models. Likewise, this rarity results in severe class imbalance, as EEG segments corresponding to seizures represent a negligible minority compared to non-seizure segments in existing datasets [89, 90]. As a result, the machine learning model tends to optimize parameters to reduce errors in the majority class while neglecting seizure events [91-93]. This bias can cause the model to consistently predict the absence of seizures, reducing training error but leading to poor performance in detecting actual seizure events, thus reducing their sensitivity and clinical effectiveness [94, 95]. Proposed solution: To address

this challenge, data augmentation techniques such as interpolation, generative adversarial networks (GANs), and generative diffusion models can be employed to increase the volume of training data, thereby enhancing model robustness and generalization capability [83,84,85]. Complementarily, oversampling methods such as Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) and Adaptive Synthetic Sampling (ADASYN) mitigate class imbalance by generating synthetic EEG segments that mimic real preictal events [96,97]. This strengthens the representation of epileptic episodes within the training set and enables models to learn discriminative patterns more effectively. Together, these techniques enhance predictive performance against epileptic events by increasing sensitivity and specificity, ultimately improving their clinical applicability in real-world scenarios [88]. Additionally, it is recommended to improve data collection through multi-center collaboration among research institutions in the field [86,87].

3.1.2. Data Heterogeneity

It refers to the significant variability in EEG data across individuals due to factors such as age, sex, medication, electrode placement, and other physiological differences [103,104]. This variability can reduce the model performance when the given seizure prediction model is applied to new individuals because the model may not take into account a high level of patient-specificity [105]. To illustrate, ML/DL models trained on EEG records from adults may not perform well on pediatric data. This contrast in outcomes may be caused by differences in brain development and/or seizure patterns [95]. Proposed Solution: In order to deal with this cause or the resulting main barrier, transfer learning can be used to adapt pretrained models to higher subgroups specificity, splitting based on different age ranges or sexes [85]. Transfer learning has shown promise in improving model accuracy by fine-tuning parameters to reflect specific patient characteristics. Additionally, creating stratified datasets that represent diverse populations (e.g., age and sex-specific data) and developing personalized models that take these factors into account can further enhance the model's ability to generalize across different patient groups [98].

3.1.3. High dimensionality of EEG

High dimensionality arises from the simultaneous recording of multiple electrodes, where the signals from each channel, although interrelated, add complexity to the system [133]. This generates a feature vector with a high number of variables, which considerably increases the computational burden [52]. Consequently, classification and pattern recognition are difficult, reducing efficiency in both training and real-time prediction [52]. Regarding the latter, EEG studies typically last from minutes to hours or even days, and are usually recorded with high sampling rates, which further increases the volume of data to be processed [135]. Proposed solution: To mitigate this problem, dimensionality reduction techniques with minimal loss of information are applied, including principal component analysis (PCA), wavelet transform (WT), and, more recently, neural networks, which allow the most relevant features to be extracted [134], [136].

3.1.4. Artifact removal for Specific source

The noisy nature of EEG signals represents a critical challenge for preprocessing [47,98,99]. Therefore, traditional techniques such as regression methods, Wavelet Transform (WT), Fourier Transformation (FT) are often useful for removing particular types of noise such as eye movement, muscle movement, ECG, etc [47]. However, they are not usually effective in removing multiple sources of artifacts that simultaneously affect the signal, and may even confuse noisy and non-noisy signals [47]. As a result, they generate a low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) when applied, which leads to poor performance in later stages, such as model training [106]. Given this, researchers have proposed using deep learning-based techniques to automate artifact detection, because they require little or no preprocessing and are resistant to noise even adapting to different artifacts, which makes them valuable for seizure prediction [107].

3.1.5. Artifact removal for Multiple Sources

Noise in EEG signals is becoming a critical challenge since they are often exposed simultaneously to multiple sources of physiological and environmental interference, making it increasingly difficult to detect seizure-associated patterns [137]. Therefore, to take advantage of the specific advantages of various techniques to optimize EEG signal preprocessing, hybrid methods such as Empirical Mode Decomposition-Blind Source

Separation (EMD-BSS), Wavelet-based BSS, BSS-SVM, and even the use of ICA and its variants have been developed [47, 143]. These approaches have demonstrated superior performance in improving signal quality, although they usually involve more complex and sophisticated algorithms, which lead to higher computational costs and, therefore, lower efficiency [47]. In response to these limitations, machine learning approaches, especially deep learning models such as CNNs [144], are emerging as more efficient alternatives [47], due to their intermediate level of complexity and great adaptability to noise levels.

3.1.6. Domain-Biased Feature Engineering

Although patient-specific feature extraction techniques have achieved high metrics in seizure prediction using particular datasets [108,109], this success is partly due to the manual intervention of experts in the feature extraction process. This involves treating each patient individually, adding a subjective component due to the variability and complexity of the behavior of the EEG signal in the same patient and between patients with epilepsy evidenced by dynamic changes in brain activity requires considerable adjustments [110] [57]. However, these techniques often lose reliability and reproducibility when tested on other datasets and suffer from poor performance [111,112,113,114] [58]. Proposed Solution: To address this challenge, researchers have proposed automating the process using deep learning techniques, which would enable direct extraction of features from raw EEG signals, aiming to develop more generalized and unified methods [115,116,117].

3.1.7. Hypothesis complexity

This problem highlights how network size affects model performance [118]. While a larger network can reduce approximation error and capture features more effectively, beyond a certain point its generalization capacity decreases, resulting in overfitting and greater computational demands, thus affecting performance [119]. A concrete example of this phenomenon is observed in deep learning models such as LSTM networks, RNNs, or hybrid CNN-LSTM architectures, which, by having multiple layers and a large number of parameters, require intensive training and consume significant time and energy resources, especially in continuous EEG monitoring applications [145,146]. Proposed solution: It is recommended to use techniques such as cross-validation to determine the optimal network size [120,121], along with regularization methods (L1, L2, or dropout), pruning, quantization, and dimensionality reduction (PCA), which allow controlling complexity while maintaining robust and clinically applicable performance [122], [147], [148].

3.1.8. Classifier not suited for time-series data

Seizure prediction depends on capturing temporal patterns in EEG data, which reflect the sequential changes in brain activity leading up to a seizure [28,76,123]. If the classifier used does not properly account for in-depth temporal dynamics—such as when models not designed for comprehensive temporal analysis-suitable high-quality data are employed—it may fail to recognize critical time-dependent patterns [124]. As a result, ignoring these dependencies can lead to inaccurate predictions, as the model might miss the subtle changes over time that signal an impending seizure, thereby compromising the overall performance and reliability of the prediction system [124,125]. Proposed Solution: A feasible solution to deal with this difficulty is to exert models particularly fabricated for time-series data that can successfully capture temporal dependencies and continuous patterns in EEG data. Techniques such as RNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs are pertinent for this task, since they are proficient in learning the convoluted temporal dynamics that antecede

seizures [42]. Also, joining these models with feature extraction techniques that point up time-dependent attributes can further boost the predictive accuracy [126,127]. Up to date techniques, like attention mechanisms, can also be included to aid the model focus on decisive time spans within the data, making sure that fine changes are not overlooked [94]. Carrying out these solutions can improve the model’s ability to notice early warning signs of seizures, leading to more attested and accurate predictions.

3.1.9. Inadequate Signal Filtering

The filters applied after the classification step might be immoderately simplistic or stiff, leading to the loss of paramount EEG signal data. If these filters are not forged to properly capture the subtleties of the EEG records, this can bring about missed seizure events or false positives [24]. Contrariwise, filters that are too complex or specifically customized

to the training data can give rise to overfitting, reducing the model’s ability to generalize to new patients or different data records [128]. Proposed Solution: Inject filters that can dynamically tune based on the patient’s specific EEG traits, rather than using fixed, rigid filters. For example, techniques like variable-frequency complex demodulation (VFCDM) have unveiled flair in maintaining high-resolution time-frequency domain analysis, dynamically calibrating the filters based on signal characteristics to better apprehend critical EEG features without losing prime data or overfitting to noise [129]. Apply robust cross-validation techniques to evaluate filter performance across different datasets. This ensures that the filters generalize well and reduce overfitting issues.

3.1.10. Inflexible Thresholding

Many seizure prediction models use post processing thresholds to classify whether a seizure event is likely or not. These thresholds may be static or set too conservatively, leading to either a high false-positive rate (too many non-seizure events being flagged) or a high false-negative rate (missing true seizure events). Ideally, thresholds should adapt based on patient-specific characteristics, but if this adaptation is neglected, performance can suffer [130]. Proposed Solution: Instead of using static thresholds, a more effective solution is to implement dynamic thresholding that adapts based on patient-specific EEG characteristics. Machine learning models can be trained to adjust thresholds in real-time based on ongoing signal analysis. For instance, an adaptive threshold system that continuously learns from patient-specific EEG data could adjust based on the frequency or intensity of preictal signals, reducing false positives or negatives [10]. Bayesian updating could also be used to adjust thresholds probabilistically, where prior knowledge of seizure occurrences (based on patient history) updates the likelihood of an event as new EEG data is received [131]. This probabilistic thresholding could improve model performance by continuously refining seizure predictions based on the latest data available.

3.1.11. Threshold misalignment

If the classifier uses a low probability threshold to determine preictal states, it may classify states as preictal even when the probability is only slightly above zero. This can result in the overclassification of states as preictal, including those with weak or non-indicative signals that do not precede an impending seizure. This misalignment results in a higher rate of false positives, where benign or non-critical signals are incorrectly labeled as preictal. Consequently, the performance of the classifier suffers, as it produces more false alarms and reduces its overall reliability and effectiveness in accurately predicting seizures. Proposed Solutions: Using techniques such as receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis

helps to find an optimal threshold that balances sensitivity (true positive rate) and specificity (false positive rate). This approach helps in setting a threshold that minimizes false positives while maintaining high predictive accuracy. Introduce post-processing

algorithms, such as smoothing filters or refractory periods, to reduce the impact of transient, weak signals being classified as preictal. These methods can help filter out noise and reduce false positives by confirming the presence of consistent patterns over time.

3.1.12. Majestic memory dependency

Memory impediments in DL models like LSTMs, GRUs, or hybrid architectures emerge from the need to keep and refresh hidden states in the course of time, principally for EEG seizure prediction. Processing time series data entails storing past inputs, enlarging memory usage considerably. The problem aggravates with prolonged continuous monitoring, struggling devices with narrowed memory, including mobile or wearable platforms. This can result in bottlenecks that lessen inference speed and make instantaneous predictions challenging except if optimized approaches, like state reduction or model compression, are executed [149]. Proposed Solutions: By virtue of pruning, it is feasible to clear away needless connections in neural networks, shrinking memory consumption while keeping accuracy [150]. On top of that, quantization drops the precision of parameters (e.g., from 32-bit to 8-bit), diminishing memory usage and computational requirements without affecting performance seriously [151]. Disposing models on peripheral devices for real-time predictions and unload computationally dense tasks to the cloud, refining both speed and memory efficiency [152,153].

3.1.13. Thresholding and Decision Making

Plenty of seizure prediction systems count on setting thresholds for classifying seizure events built on model outputs (e.g., probabilities). Inappropriate threshold settings can bring on either intemperate false positives or overlooked seizures, entailing further computations to optimize these thresholds. This can hold up response times and need supplemental tuning of the model. Proposed Solutions: Rather than implementing fixed thresholds for decision-making, adaptive thresholding can dynamically calibrate based on instantaneous data characteristics. This line of action permits for more plastic returns to differing EEG signal setup, likely decreasing false positives and missed seizures. For example, techniques like dynamic programming or machine learning-based approaches can amend thresholds based on the ongoing context, hence improving the model’s sensibility and accuracy [154]. Employing extra contextual data, such as medical history, preceding seizure patterns or real-time physiological metrics can boost the decision-making process. Including these details into the thresholding basis can give rise to more informed predictions and lessens the dependency on inflexible thresholds. This outlook can also help tailor predictions to individual patients, upgrading both efficiency and accuracy [154].

3.2. Clinical Viability Layer: Utility–Latency Feasibility Region as a Clinically Grounded

Evaluation Criterion

While the pipeline-based problems described in Section 3.1 explain how technical limitations emerge during model development, they do not by themselves determine whether a seizure prediction system is clinically useful. In practice, a model may achieve encouraging classification metrics and still fail to provide meaningful benefit to patients if it generates too many false alarms or if predictions are delivered too late to enable intervention. To bridge

this gap, we introduce a clinical viability layer that complements the causal taxonomy with a clinically grounded evaluation criterion.

The central idea is that seizure prediction performance should not be judged only by conventional machine learning metrics (e.g., accuracy, F1-score, or AUC), but also by whether the system satisfies two minimum clinical requirements: utility (the prediction must provide more benefit than harm) and latency (the warning must be delivered early enough to be actionable). These two requirements define a utility–Latency feasibility region, which provides a practical framework for assessing the translational potential of EEG-based seizure prediction methods.

3.2.1. Utility feasibility constraint (clinical benefit vs. false alarm burden)

A seizure prediction system is clinically meaningful only if the expected benefit of true warnings outweighs the burden imposed by false alarms. This is particularly important in epilepsy, where excessive false alerts may cause alarm fatigue, anxiety, reduced adherence, and eventual rejection of the system by patients and caregivers. Therefore, a clinically grounded evaluation must explicitly incorporate the trade-off between sensitivity and false prediction rate.

Let S denote seizure frequency (e.g., seizures/day), TPR the true positive rate (sensitivity), and FPR the false prediction rate (e.g., false alarms/day). Let BTP represent the benefit associated with a correct warning and CFP the cost associated with a false warning. A minimal net utility criterion can be expressed as:

$$U = S \cdot \text{TPR} \cdot \text{BTP} - \text{FPR} \cdot \text{CFP}.$$

Clinical viability requires $U > 0$, which yields:

$$S \cdot \text{TPR} \cdot \text{BTP} > \text{FPR} \cdot \text{CFP}.$$

Defining the cost–benefit ratio as $R = \text{CFP}/\text{BTP}$, the condition can be rewritten as:

$$\text{FPR} S \text{ TPR} < R$$

This inequality defines a utility boundary that is directly interpretable in clinical terms. It shows that the acceptable false prediction burden depends not only on model sensitivity, but also on seizure frequency and the relative cost of false alarms. As a result, the same model may be clinically viable for one patient (e.g., higher seizure frequency or higher warning benefit) and clinically non-viable for another. This observation is espe-

cially relevant for comparing studies across heterogeneous patient cohorts and motivates reporting FPR in clinically interpretable units (e.g., false alarms/day) rather than relying solely on aggregate classification metrics.

3.2.2. Latency feasibility constraint (actionable warning time)

In addition to utility, a seizure prediction system must satisfy a latency requirement: predictions must be generated early enough to allow a clinically useful response (e.g., behavioral adaptation, caregiver notification, or device-triggered intervention). Even a highly accurate model may fail in practice if the warning is issued too late.

Let L_{sys} denote the total system latency and W_{req} the minimum warning time required for action. Let LT_{total} denote the total available lead time before seizure onset. A basic latency feasibility condition is:

$$L_{\text{sys}} + W_{\text{req}} < LT_{\text{total}}.$$

To connect this condition to model and pipeline design, L_{sys} can be decomposed as:

$$L_{\text{sys}} = L_{\text{eng}} + T_{\text{conf}},$$

where L_{eng} is the engineering/computational latency (signal acquisition, preprocessing, inference, communication), and T_{conf} is the confirmation delay introduced by post-processing and decision logic (e.g., smoothing windows, refractory periods, threshold persistence rules). This decomposition is important because many strategies used to reduce false positives (Section 3.1.9–3.1.13) increase T_{conf} , thereby improving apparent classification stability while potentially violating actionability constraints.

If the available lead time varies across seizures, a conservative requirement can be defined using a quantile q_{α} of the lead-time distribution:

$$L_{\text{sys}} < q_{\alpha} - W_{\text{req}}.$$

This expression provides a critical latency bound and makes the engineering implications explicit: if $q_{\alpha} - W_{\text{req}}$ is small, only low-latency pipelines are clinically feasible, regardless of nominal classification performance.

3.2.3. Utility–Latency feasibility region and its role in the causal

framework

Taken together, the utility and latency constraints define a utility–latency feasibility region: a seizure prediction system is clinically viable only if it is both beneficial (positive expected utility) and actionable (sufficient warning time after accounting for system latency). Conceptually, this region serves as a translational filter between algorithmic performance and clinical applicability.

This viability layer complements the pipeline-based/non-pipeline-based taxonomy in three ways. First, it explains why improvements in conventional metrics do not always translate to clinical value. Second, it reveals an important trade-off: methods that reduce false alarms through aggressive post-processing or threshold tuning may simultaneously increase confirmation delay, pushing the system outside the latency-feasible region. Third, it provides a common evaluation lens for comparing models developed under different datasets and

protocols, thereby addressing part of the comparability problem discussed later in non-pipeline-based issues.

In this sense, the utility–latency feasibility region does not replace existing ML evaluation metrics; rather, it contextualizes them under clinical requirements. It is therefore particularly useful as a bridge between technical pipeline optimization and broader methodological concerns such as standardization, interpretability, and transparency.

Figure 3: Schematic visualization of the proposed Utility–Latency feasibility framework. (a) A model is utility-feasible if its operating point lies below the utility boundary $FPR = (S/R)TPR$. (b) Clinical viability requires satisfying both a utility constraint and a latency constraint, yielding the shaded feasibility region.

The practical implications of this clinical viability layer for evaluation and reporting are discussed in Section 3.3.1, within the broader problem of the lack of a comprehensive evaluation framework.

3.3. Non Pipeline-based problems

Beyond the algorithmic pipeline, several systemic and methodological barriers hinder the practical deployment of seizure prediction models (Figure 3). These include inconsistencies in evaluation protocols, lack of standardization among methodologies, and the limited interpretability of deep learning architectures. Collectively, these non-pipeline-based issues reflect structural weaknesses in the field rather than specific algorithmic flaws.

Figure 4: Non pipeline-based problems and their solutions in machine learning methods for seizure prediction using EEG signals

3.3.1. Lack of a comprehensive evaluation framework

Numerous studies employ a wide variety of metrics to evaluate seizure prediction models, including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score [23]. The choice of evaluation criteria can substantially alter the perceived performance of a model, making comparisons across studies difficult and sometimes misleading. A model may appear competitive under one metric while performing poorly under another, thereby complicating evidence-based selection and interpretation by researchers and clinicians [160].

In addition, model comparison is often centered only on predictive performance, while overlooking efficiency-related parameters. This omission is critical, since more complex models—especially deep learning architectures—often require substantial computational resources, long training times, and expensive hyperparameter tuning procedures. These demands may involve specialized hardware (e.g., GPUs/TPUs) and large datasets, increasing implementation cost and limiting reproducibility and deployability [161]. As a result, the field lacks a unified framework that jointly evaluates performance, efficiency, and clinical usability.

A further limitation is that many studies report conventional machine learning metrics without explicitly assessing whether the prediction system is clinically viable. As discussed in Section 3.2, a clinically useful seizure prediction method should satisfy not only classification performance requirements, but also utility and latency constraints. In other words, strong performance metrics alone do not guarantee clinical relevance if the model

produces excessive false alarms or if predictions are not delivered with sufficient lead time. Therefore, evaluation frameworks should incorporate clinically grounded criteria in addition to standard statistical measures.

From this perspective, the proposed utility–latency feasibility region provides a complementary evaluation lens for interpreting model performance under real-world clinical requirements. This framework highlights that the clinical value of a seizure prediction system depends on at least two additional dimensions beyond conventional metrics: (i) the balance between true warnings and false prediction burden, and (ii) the ability to deliver warnings early enough for action. Integrating these dimensions into evaluation would improve comparability across studies and reduce the current disconnect between reported performance and clinical applicability.

Proposed solution: A more comprehensive and standardized evaluation framework should combine traditional predictive metrics, efficiency metrics, and clinically grounded reporting variables. In particular, studies should consistently report sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and false prediction rate, while also including execution time and memory usage to enable fair comparison among architectures [115,161]. To support clinical interpretation and translational assessment, we further recommend reporting at minimum: (i) TPR, (ii) FPR in clinically interpretable units (e.g., false alarms/day), (iii) seizure frequency S or stratification by seizure burden, (iv) post-processing and thresholding rules, and (v) latency decomposition (Leng, Tconf, and total Lsys). These quantities allow a preliminary assessment of whether a model plausibly lies within the proposed utility–latency feasibility region, thereby improving both methodological rigor and clinical relevance.

3.2.2. Lack of standardization

Research on seizure prediction faces a limited standardization of training norms and protocols [23,162]. The heterogeneity of datasets, diversity of preprocessing techniques, and varied experimental configurations can lead to contradictory results, compromising the external validity of conclusions [162]. Furthermore, the diversity of architectures, ranging from classical machine learning (ML) approaches to complex deep learning (DL) models, introduces specific strengths and limitations associated with each method. Although hybrid models are designed to combine the advantages of multiple approaches, they add additional complexity that affects reproducibility and systematic comparison [155,156]. Proposed solution: In response to this challenge, the adoption of publicly available and widely used datasets, such as CHB-MIT, the Freiburg EEG Dataset, or EPILEPSIAE, is recommended to enable model training and validation under comparable conditions with greater clinical diversity [23,163]. Similarly, implementing a standardized preprocessing pipeline—including band-pass filtering between 0.5 and 40 Hz, artifact removal using techniques such as Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and normalization through Z-score or Min–Max scaling—would help reduce variability in data preparation [30]. Standardization should also extend to the feature extraction and selection processes, where the employed features must be explicitly reported. Finally, the use of standardized

reporting formats for model architectures, hyperparameters, training procedures, and computational resources would promote transparency and reproducibility in ML and DL research for seizure prediction. For instance, in this direction, the proposed EEG ML Model Card provides a reference framework to enhance reliability and transparency in machine learning research applied to EEG [XYZ].

3.2.3. Lack of interpretability in deep learning models

Many deep learning models, such as CNNs and RNNs like LSTMs, have been applied to seizure prediction using electroencephalogram data. However, these models are often seen

as "black boxes" weakening the confidence of clinicians in making high-risk decisions based on their outputs [166], especially when they fail [167]. The challenge arises because these models learn representations from the data through multiple processing complex layers [168], without offering clear explanations for their predictions. For example, a neural network might predict an imminent seizure, but it is not clear which features or patterns in the EEG data contributed to this outcome. As a result, in the task of seizure prediction, the explainability in decision making and its influence on the improvement of the developed models takes on an important role [166], especially for improving clinical acceptance due to better interpretability [169]. Proposed solution: To address this, researchers have been developed interpretable learning classifiers [170], even associating certain properties of the model's behavior with expert medical knowledge [171].

3.2.4. Lack of transparency in feature learning

Seizure prediction models use EEG data as an entry, which is very dependent on time and multidimensional, for this reason, when we use training classifiers, this non-linear information must be compacted in some characteristics. However, many times the disconnection between the characteristics extracted and their physiological meaning increases the lack of interpretability. Multiple feature extraction methods and classifiers have been evaluated to identify the optimal combinations for each patient [109 ,108], however it is not known what this accuracy is, which increases the lack of transparency. This issue is highly relevant in the medical sector, where reliability and transparency in decision making are paramount [172]. One factor for demanding a high level of transparency comes from the adverse consequences of a wrong diagnosis or prediction [173]. Proposed solution: In light of this, researchers propose using end-to-end explainable classification techniques complemented by a graphical representation to help facilitate interpretation [174].

3.2.5. Spurious Correlations

Deep learning models can sometimes detect spurious patterns or overfit to noise in EEG signals, as has been observed in machine learning models when learning spurious correla-

tions that are unrelated to the underlying clinical decision [175,176]. These correlations contribute to model fragility and poor performance in case of domain shifts [106]. Algorithms rely on a set of assumptions to make predictions of new data, referred to as inductive bias [106]. But, when this bias aligns closely with spurious patterns, it leads to overfitting and poor generalization [106]. For example, an unbalanced chest X-ray imaging pneumonia classifier was observed to use metadata in its prediction [177]. This is evidence that classifiers working well with training and validation data are not exempt from falling into incorrect logic when incorporated into the clinical part [174]. Proposed solution: Given this, it has been proposed to use a framework that spans the entire eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) lifecycle to identify, mitigate and re-evaluate spurious behavior in models [175].

4. Discussion:

4.1. Clinical viability interpretation: the utility-latency feasibility region

Despite substantial methodological progress, the seizure prediction literature continues to show a persistent translational gap: models may achieve encouraging statistical performance in retrospective or experimentally controlled settings, yet still fail to produce meaningful benefit in routine clinical use. This concern is consistent with prior work on seizure advisory systems and later reviews of the field, which emphasize that the relevant question is not only whether seizures can be statistically anticipated, but whether the resulting warnings are sufficiently reliable, interpretable, and actionable to improve patient management in practice. In this sense, the proposed utility–latency feasibility region should be understood not as a replacement for conventional predictive metrics, but as a clinically grounded overlay that asks whether a statistically successful model is also usable at the bedside or in long-term ambulatory care (Cook et al.,2013).

From a clinical perspective, false alarms are not a minor technical inconvenience. Existing studies indicate that excessive false predictions can undermine the purpose of seizure warning devices by causing unnecessary stress, habituation to alarms, and reduced confidence in the system. This is why several authors have argued that false prediction burden must be expressed in clinically interpretable units and judged relative to patient context rather than in isolation. Earlier work even suggested that false prediction rates above roughly 0.15/h are questionable outside closed-loop intervention settings, while more recent calibration studies show that strong reductions in false alarm rate may be achievable only at the cost of missed seizures. Taken together, these findings support the central intuition of our framework: clinical viability depends on the balance between benefit and burden, and the same operating point may be acceptable for one patient subgroup but unacceptable for another, especially when seizure frequency is low and false alarms become intolerable (Gadhoumi et al., 2015)

Our proposal also aligns with, but is distinct from, the recent shift from alarm-based seizure prediction toward probabilistic seizure forecasting. Recent comparative work argues that forecasting may be more suitable than crisp prediction for warning devices because it replaces binary alarms with continuously updated risk estimates and may reduce the harmful effects of repeated false alerts. Likewise, a 2024 systematic review and meta-analysis of automated seizure forecasting reported only moderate pooled discrimination and highlighted severe heterogeneity in datasets, train–test design, forecast horizons, and performance metrics. Against this background, the utility–latency feasibility region offers a complementary contribution: rather than choosing between prediction and forecasting as competing paradigms, it provides a common clinical lens through which both can be judged—namely, whether the output is beneficial enough and early enough to support action (Costa et al., 2024).

In addition to utility, clinical value requires timeliness. A warning delivered too close to seizure onset may be statistically correct but clinically ineffective. The latency constraint highlights that feasibility depends not only on model inference speed but also on delays introduced by the full pipeline. Importantly, system latency can be decomposed into engineering latency and confirmation delay. This decomposition is critical because many techniques designed to reduce false alarms such as smoothing or confirmation windows can increase T_{conf} , pushing a method outside the latency-feasible region even if conventional classification metrics improve. (Andrade et al., 2024).

Finally, the feasibility perspective helps explain why evaluation inconsistency remains such a major obstacle to translation. Recent methodological work has shown that apparently strong seizure prediction performance can collapse when more rigorous patient-independent

validation is used; in one study, accuracy fell from about 80% to 50% under leave-one-patient-out evaluation. Reviews and meta-analyses further report substantial heterogeneity in datasets, preprocessing, horizons, retrospective versus pseudo-prospective validation, and deterministic versus probabilistic metrics. This means that models cannot be fairly compared on the basis of accuracy, AUC, or sensitivity alone. In our view, this is precisely where the utility–latency feasibility region becomes useful: it reframes comparison around clinically interpretable quantities—false alarm burden, warning timing, and practical actionability—while remaining compatible with standard ML reporting. Thus, the framework is not intended to replace established evaluation practice, but to make explicit the clinical conditions under which an algorithmic result becomes plausibly translatable (Shafieezadeh et al., 2023).

4.2. Trust and Transparency

Interpretable models allow clinicians to understand which EEG patterns or data features contribute to seizure predictions, an essential aspect for fostering trust in clinical settings [193]. Transparency allows the verification of a model alignment with neurological

knowledge and clinical reasoning. Therefore, transparency ensures that the insights from the seizure prediction model are credible. By recognizing specific patterns in data that impact predictions such as changes in frequency bands, signal amplitude, interpretable models can give a deeper grasp of the neurological processes underlying seizures [194].

Additionally, interpretability helps identify potential errors or biases within the decision-making process of the model, boosting reliability across diverse EEG records [195]. When clinicians can comprehend the rationale behind predictions, the collaboration between AI tools and medical professionals will be facilitated, supporting more confident and informed decision-making [196,197].

4.3. Reduction of False Positives and Negatives

Balancing sensitivity (catching true seizures) and specificity (minimizing false alarms) is critical in seizure prediction, as both metrics directly impact patient care and outcomes [98]. Interpretable models facilitate this balance by making it easier to adjust thresholds and analyze patterns, allowing clinicians to fine-tune model parameters to achieve optimal performance tailored to individual patient profiles. By understanding which features drive predictions, clinicians could adjust the model to be more or less conservative, depending on the patient's risk tolerance and clinical scenario. Reducing false positives not only prevents unnecessary alarms that can cause patient anxiety and disrupt daily activities but also reduces caregiver fatigue, especially in home monitoring settings. Similarly, minimizing false negatives ensures that critical seizure events are not missed, thereby enabling timely medical interventions that could prevent complications [199]. Thus, interpretable models contribute to a higher quality of life by enhancing the reliability of seizure prediction systems, fostering patient safety, and supporting personalized treatment strategies.

4.4. Personalization of Care

The inter- and intra-individual variability in the electrical activity of the brain of patients with epilepsy, added to the fact that this chronic disease manifests itself in a unique and different way in each human being depending on the type of seizure, frequency of epileptic seizures

and other factors, merits personalized care, that is, adapted to the specific characteristics of each patient in order to obtain possible better clinical results for the benefit of a better quality of life for them. Although patient-specific models have been developed for seizure prediction using EEG signals, these are prone to overfitting due to the excessive use of the limited data available for training [200]. On the other hand, interpretability could help adapt treatments to each patient by allowing doctors to see how specific EEG characteristics influence seizure predictions and thus be able to carry out personalized treatment and monitoring [170].

However, it is still difficult to establish closer and more effective collaboration between epileptologists and computer scientists to face these challenges together.

4.5. Enhanced Real-Time Monitoring

Real-time or low-latency monitoring for epilepsy treatment is essential to improve the area of seizure prediction. The use of portable EEG devices interconnected with others through IoT presents significant potential to increase the capacity of ML/DL for seizure prediction [201], as has already been shown for ECG signals [202]. To carry out this translation of software to clinical application, hardware with specific characteristics is required, including cost-effectiveness, low energy consumption, and high computational efficiency, as well as high performance by the ML/DL model [201]. The integration of software and hardware represents a transcendental step to close the gap between advanced models and implementation in clinical practices.

Conclusions

We conclude that seizure prediction systems should be evaluated within a clinically grounded utility–latency feasibility region, because strong conventional metrics (e.g., AUC/F1) do not guarantee real-world benefit if false alarms dominate expected utility or if warnings are delivered too late to be actionable.

The feasibility framework reveals a fundamental trade-off between false-alarm control and actionability: post-processing and thresholding strategies that reduce false positives often increase confirmation delay T_{conf} , which can violate latency constraints even when classification performance improves. Therefore, studies should report FPR in clinical units (e.g., false alarms/day) and latency components (L_{sys} , L_{eng} , T_{conf}) to support fair comparison and clinical translation.

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